

1 **Supplementary figures**

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3 **Figure S1. a.** Distribution of “true” origination and extinction proportions generated

4 within the simulated dataset, globally (top; 10000 iterations) and for individual spatial

5 bins (bottom; 6 x 10000 = 60000 bins). b. Species abundance distributions for t_1 and

6 t_2 (the time bins for which origination and extinction were calculated), globally (2

7 x 10000 = 20000 spatio-temporal bins) and for individual spatial bins (bottom; 2 x 6 x

8 10000 = 120000 spatio-temporal bins). The black line is the mean abundance of the

9 species found at the given identity rank, with the grey error bars showing the

10 maximum and minimum abundance at that rank.

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13 *Figure S2a.* Difference between “true” and estimated proportions of origination and
 14 extinction across all spatial bins ($n = 60000$) produced in simulation.

15 *Figure S2b.* Difference between “true” and estimated proportions of origination and
 16 extinction following sampling in individual spatial bins, subdivided depending on the
 17 proportion of occurrences sampled in the focal bin (width = 20% of occurrences).

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20 *Figure S3.* Number of iterations for which the identity of the bin with minimum and
 21 maximum proportion is preserved following sampling. Boundary-crosser and three-
 22 timer methods produced identical results.

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25 *Figure S4.* Distribution of correlation coefficients and p-values across iterations when

26 comparing “true” proportions of extinction and origination to those produced post-

27 sampling and estimation. Tests examined rank correlation using Spearman’s ρ .

28 Boundary-crosser and three-timer methods produced identical results.

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31 *Figure S5.* Number of spatial bins for which proportions of origination and extinction
 32 are overestimated compared to their “true” value within a given iteration; for
 33 example, a value of six would mean that all bins in the iteration were overestimated,
 34 whereas a value of zero would mean that all bins in the iteration were
 35 underestimated.

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38 *Figure S6.* Distribution of “true” origination and extinction proportions generated
 39 within the high, medium, and low simulated datasets, globally (top; 5000 iterations)
 40 and for individual spatial bins (bottom; 6 x 5000 = 30000 bins).

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43 *Figure S7.* Species abundance distributions for t_1 and t_2 (the time bins for which

44 origination and extinction were calculated) in the high, medium, and low level

45 simulations, globally (top; $2 \times 5000 = 10000$ spatio-temporal bins) and for individual

46 spatial bins (bottom; $2 \times 6 \times 5000 = 60000$ spatio-temporal bins). The black line is the
47 mean abundance of the species found at the given identity rank, with the grey error
48 bars showing the maximum and minimum abundance at that rank.

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51 *Figure S8.* Difference between “true” and estimated proportions of origination and
52 extinction, following sampling, across all spatial bins ($n = 30000$) produced in the
53 high, medium, and low level simulations.

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56 *Figure S9.* Number of iterations in which the identity of the bin with the highest and
 57 lowest proportional extinction is identified, following sampling, for the high, medium,
 58 and low level simulations. Boundary-crosser and three-timer methods produced
 59 identical results.

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62 *Figure S10.* Distribution of correlation coefficients and p-values across high, medium
 63 and low level simulation iterations, when comparing “true” proportions of extinction
 64 and origination to those produced post-sampling and estimation. Tests examined
 65 rank correlation using Spearman’s ρ . Boundary-crosser and three-timer methods
 66 produced identical results.

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69 *Figure S11.* Distribution of number of spatial bins for which proportions of origination

70 and extinction were overestimated compared to their “true” value within a given

71 iteration in the high, medium and low level simulations; for example, a value of six

72 would mean that all bins in the iteration were overestimated, whereas a value of zero

73 would mean that all bins in the iteration were either estimated correctly or

74 underestimated.

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77 *Figure S12.* Effects of abundance selectivity, sampling intensity of t_0 , t_1 , and t_2 time

78 bins, and extinction metric on the bias in observed extinction rate.

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81 *Figure S13.* Estimates rates of species-level origination and extinction by latitude for

82 four different marine clades in each stage of the Middle Permian to Middle Triassic.

83 Occurrences were split into six 30° latitude bins. Estimates were calculated for each

- 84 spatio-temporal bin containing five or more species. Missing points indicate
- 85 insufficient occurrences to calculate a proportion.